

ONLINE TEACHING AND LEARNING CHALLENGES DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC FOR PRESCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic necessitated a shift to online teaching and learning, including in preschool education. However, this transition brought about various challenges for preschool teachers, affecting both their teaching practices and students' engagement. This study aims to investigate the challenges faced by preschool teachers during online teaching amid the COVID-19 pandemic, explore the strategies they employ to overcome these challenges, and understand their perceptions of online teaching and learning. Data from 70 preschool teachers from different schools were collected through a quantitative approach using a questionnaire. The survey findings revealed that teachers faced difficulties using the technical instruments due to a lack of training. Additionally, students experienced boredom and disengagement during online classes, and teachers struggled to effectively deliver educational content through digital technologies. Moreover, a lack of knowledge was observed in transforming offline resources into online materials and sharing them on e-learning platforms. The research employed a quantitative method, utilizing closed-ended questions in a questionnaire format. The questionnaires were administered to respondents who agreed to participate in the study through Google Forms, adhering to pandemic restrictions. The research recruitment was carried out through various channels, including Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, Email, Short Message Service (SMS), and Instagram. To address the challenges of online teaching and learning during the pandemic, preschool teachers need to have a backup plan and test content before video lectures. Further research is essential to explore other potential challenges impacting online education sessions led by preschool teachers.

Keywords: online teaching, preschool teachers, COVID-19 pandemic, students' engagement, online education

INTRODUCTION

Online learning, a form of remote education, has been part of the American educational system for some time, and it gained significant prominence during the COVID-19 pandemic as a means of facilitating continued learning (Bartley & Golek, 2004). This type of learning can be purely online courses or hybrid/blended learning, which combines face-to-face classes with online and technology-supported learning (Mornar & Boticki, 2009). During the pandemic, e-learning platforms were critical in sustaining education during school closures (Subedi et al., 2020). However, there are challenges associated with online teaching, such as reduced student-teacher interaction, distance, and the lack of contact, potentially affecting learning

efficacy compared to traditional methods (Almosa, 2002). These challenges stem from inadequate training, facilities, and infrastructure, students' preparedness and the availability of learning tools (Munezero et al., 2016). Considering the impact of preschool teachers on young children's development, understanding their perceptions of online classes during the COVID-19 pandemic becomes crucial for supporting effective learning and well-being and shaping future generations of society. Therefore, this research aims to explore preschool teachers' challenges, strategies, and perceptions during online teaching and learning amid the current pandemic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review explores various aspects related to the challenges faced by preschool teachers during online teaching amid the COVID-19 pandemic. It begins by highlighting the need for teachers to adapt to online teaching and employ technology in education to address problems and adopt innovative educational strategies (Eickelmann & Gerick, 2020). The review then emphasises the prevalence of online learning experiences among children during the pandemic and the limited time spent on each session (Dong et al., 2020). The first challenge identified is the difficulty preschool teachers face in having the necessary digital tools to deliver effective online education. Technical issues and lack of training in using technology can lead to poor quality teaching and disrupt students' learning experiences (Sheridan, 2020). Additionally, the online learning environment may not cater to the physical engagement and activities preschool students enjoy, leading to disengagement (Sheridan, 2020). Lack of knowledge and expertise in transforming offline resources into online materials and sharing them on digital platforms further contributes to the challenges (Basilaia et al., 2020). A significant challenge is the absence of a community aspect and limited social interaction in online education. Lack of connectivity and language barriers can also hinder effective communication and understanding between teachers and students (Khan et al., 2012; Hardin et al., 2010). The shift to online teaching has also highlighted the importance of effective professional development for teachers in embracing technology (Badri et al., 2016; Omar et al., 2017). The review acknowledges monetary barriers and poor credential quality as factors affecting the implementation of in-service training for early childhood education teachers (Majzub, 2013). Teachers with English as a second language may face language barriers when engaging in professional development activities (Hardin et al., 2010). The review proposes several strategies to address the challenges of online teaching. Teachers can employ video lectures with proper proceedings, have backup plans, and test content before lessons to avoid distractions and technical issues (Georgiev & Nikolova, 2020). Online activities can be designed to be attractive and engaging, capturing students' attention and promoting active participation. Teachers should also focus on building professional solid identities and developing competencies in online teaching approaches (Manca & Meluzzi, 2020; Carroll et al., 2009). The review emphasises the significance of preschool teachers' acceptance and willingness to embrace technology for successful online education (Dong, 2018). Investigating preschool teachers' attitudes and readiness towards online learning is crucial for effective implementation (Noreen et al., 2019). The literature review points out the lack of research on the perceptions and attitudes of preschool teachers towards online learning and digitization in early childhood education (Noreen & Gulzar, 2019). It also highlights the uniqueness of a study by Wingo, N. P., Ivankova, N. V., & Moss, J. A. (2017) addressing teacher-student perception gaps and performance expectations in online courses. Overall, the literature review provides valuable insights into the challenges faced by preschool teachers during online teaching and the strategies that can be employed to overcome these challenges. It also identifies gaps in the field, particularly the need for more research on teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards online learning in early childhood education.

METHODOLOGY

This study's research design involved combining qualitative and quantitative research with a descriptive approach. The combination of qualitative and quantitative methods allows for a comprehensive understanding of the perceptions and attitudes of preschool teachers in Malaysia regarding the challenges of online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. The descriptive approach provides a detailed account of the participants' responses, opinions, and experiences. The theoretical framework for this study was inferred that the research draws on relevant theories related to online education, technology acceptance, and pedagogical practices in early childhood education. For instance, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is relevant to understanding how preschool teachers perceive and adopt online education technologies. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a popular theoretical framework used to understand and predict users' acceptance and adoption of new information technology (IT) systems. Developed by Fred Davis in 1989 and later extended by Fred Davis and Venkatesh, TAM posits that two primary factors influence users' intention to use technology. The first factor is Perceived Usefulness (PU), which refers to the extent to which users believe that a particular technology will enhance their job performance or make their tasks more efficient and effective. The second factor is Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), which relates to users' perception of how easy and effortless it is to use the technology (Venkatesh et al.; X., 2012). When users perceive a technology as useful and easy to use, they are more likely to develop a positive attitude towards it, leading to a higher intention to use it. This, in turn, influences their actual usage behavior of the technology. As a widely recognized model, TAM has been applied in numerous studies across domains to gain insights into users' behavior and acceptance of various technologies. Researchers and practitioners use TAM to identify potential barriers to adoption and devise strategies to enhance users' acceptance and utilization of technology. The conceptual framework of the study may be guided by the concepts related to challenges in online education, strategies for overcoming difficulties, and factors influencing the effectiveness of online teaching in preschools during the COVID-19 pandemic. The conceptual framework includes components related to the socio-demographic background of the teachers and how it influences their perceptions and attitudes towards online education. Data collection for this study involved an online survey administered through Google Forms. The survey consisted of closed-ended and agreement scale-based questions on a five-point scale, allowing for quantitative data to be collected. The survey addressed various aspects, including perceptions of online education, ease of use, challenges during COVID-19, and strategies to overcome difficulties. The sampling frame includes preschool teachers in Malaysia who have used the online method of teaching during the pandemic. 70 teachers from private and government schools participated in the study, ensuring representation from different types of schools. A pre-test was conducted with a small group of respondents to evaluate the clarity and validity of the questionnaire. Any unclear questions were paraphrased, and the questionnaire was reviewed by a research specialist and the researcher's academic supervisor to ensure content legitimacy. The collected data will be cleaned, edited, and coded using the statistical program SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 24. Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, and standard deviation are used to summarize the data and understand its characteristics. The cluster analysis method recognises patterns related to each research objective. The study results were presented using tables and figures, offering a clear and visual representation of the findings. Overall, this research design aims to comprehensively understand preschool teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards online education during the COVID-19 pandemic, using a mixed-method approach that combines qualitative and quantitative data. The chosen data collection and analysis methods will help shed light on the challenges preschool teachers face and their strategies to cope with online teaching difficulties.

RESULTS

The research findings of this study aimed to establish preschool teachers' perceptions regarding online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in Malaysia. The section addressed three research questions. The findings revealed that preschool teachers encountered various challenges during online teaching amid the pandemic. Technical issues with digital tools and a lack of training were noted, leading to difficulties in delivering high-quality teaching services and disruptions in students' learning experiences. Additionally, the shift to online education deprived students of physical engagement and activities, resulting in feelings of disengagement and dullness among the children. Converting offline resources to online materials and sharing them on digital platforms posed significant obstacles for the teachers, affecting their ability to accommodate students of various levels and devise appropriate teaching approaches. Moreover, the absence of a community aspect in online education and limited social interaction between teachers and students added to the challenges faced during the pandemic. The study found that preschool teachers implemented various strategies to overcome the challenges posed by online teaching and learning during COVID-19. Among these strategies, teachers emphasized the importance of having a backup plan and testing content before conducting online lessons to avoid distractions and technical issues. Teachers focused on designing attractive and interactive online activities to enhance student engagement, ensuring that students felt involved in the learning process. Personal attention to each child and setting time limits for engagement were also mentioned as effective approaches to adapt quickly to the online environment. Furthermore, the utilization of technology, such as IT personnel for technical support and the integration of music and videos, played a crucial role in keeping students actively engaged during online classes. The research findings indicated that preschool teachers' perceptions of online teaching and learning during COVID-19 were mixed. While some teachers showed willingness and acceptance towards technology, others struggled to adapt to the new online teaching methods. The study highlighted the importance of preschool teachers' attitudes and readiness in ensuring the successful implementation of digital learning. Additionally, teachers' professional development and access to training in online teaching approaches were identified as critical factors influencing their competence in navigating the challenges of online education. To analyze the data, the research utilized SPSS version 21 to modify, process, and evaluate the answered questionnaires. Descriptive statistics, including mean, frequency, and standard deviation, were employed to summarize the data and provide a clear understanding of the preschool teachers' perceptions and experiences with online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in Malaysia. Cluster analysis was applied to recognize patterns related to each research question, enabling a deeper exploration of the findings. Overall, this study shed light on the perceptions, challenges, and strategies of preschool teachers in Malaysia concerning online teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, contributing to the understanding of the implications of the sudden shift to digital education in early childhood settings.

The findings of this research indicated that 70 respondents completed and returned their surveys, resulting in a response rate of 100%. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), a statistically significant response rate for evaluation should be at a minimum of 50%. The study's findings indicated that 59% of the respondents were male, while 41% were females. This suggests that both male and female genders participated in the project, although the number of males was greater than that of females. The study findings established that 72% of the respondents fell into the age category between 20-29 years, 14% were in the age category between 30-39 years, 10% were in the age category between 40-49 years, and only 4% were above 50 years old. This indicates that the study encompassed all age groups represented in the organization. However, it was observed that most of the respondents were young, between 20 and 29 years old. The research findings showed that most preschool teachers,

comprising 52% of the respondents, had a college level of education. This was followed by 20% of respondents having a university level of education, 11% with a post-graduate level, and 17% at the secondary level. These results indicate that a significant number of respondents had college education as their highest level of education, suggesting that they were more likely to be aware of the challenges faced by preschool teachers in teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the statistics, 37% of the responders had utilized an online forum for 2-5 years. A significant portion of 34% reported using online forums for 5 years and above, while 29% had experience with online forums for less than 2 years. These results indicate that the respondents had a considerable amount of experience using online forums, which suggests that they were well-acquainted with the platform and, thus, better qualified to provide the relevant information required for this study. The research findings revealed that 95% of the responders had access to an online forum to educate preschool students, while only 5% reported having no access. This indicates that most of the preschool teachers had access to online forums for educational purposes. These findings suggest that the respondents were well-qualified to provide relevant information for this study, given their widespread use of online forums in preschool education. The findings indicated that 70% of the responders utilized Google Classroom to educate preschool students, while Zoom was used by 25% of the respondents, and Teams was used by only 5%. These results suggest that most pupils and preschool teachers were familiar with using Google Classroom for online education.

Table 1. The Challenges Preschool Teachers Face in Online Teaching and Learning.

	Mean	Std. Div.
I have a challenge with the technological tool due to lacking training on its use.	3.4143	1.29738
Students feel bored and not engaged as it is not physical learning.	3.4714	1.32667
I cannot have the digital tools to deliver legal education	3.4143	1.42943
I lack the knowledge and expertise to convert offline resources to online materials and share them.	3.4143	1.38828

The findings regarding this study's first objective explored the challenges preschool teachers faced during online teaching and learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic. The responders concurred that teachers encountered challenges with the technological tools due to a lack of training, as indicated by a total value of 3.4143 and a mean dispersion of 1.29738. Furthermore, the respondents agreed that students felt bored and disengaged during online lessons, attributing it to the absence of physical learning. The total value for this statement was 3.4714, with a mean dispersion of 1.32667. Regarding the ability of teachers to provide effective instruction, the respondents indicated a moderate lack of confidence in teachers' ability to deliver legal education, with a total value of 3.4143 and a mean dispersion of 1.42943. Lastly, in response to whether preschool teachers had the knowledge and expertise to convert offline resources to online materials and share them on e-learning platforms, the responders agreed that there was a lack of proficiency in this area. The total value for this statement was 3.4143, with a mean dispersion of 1.38828.

Table 2. Strategies for Preschool Teachers to Overcome the Challenges of Online Teaching and Learning.

	Mean	Std. Div.
I have a backup plan and testing contents during video lectures before the lessons.	2.8286	1.35102
My online programs are designed to make the child motivated to study.	3.5143	1.33561
I am trained and involved in making the strategies for educating students online.	3.6571	1.36929

Before using it, I read and understand the terms and conditions stated on online contracts. 3.1429 1.27729

The research findings concerning the second objective focused on the strategies employed by preschool teachers during online education. The responders strongly agreed that teachers had a backup plan during video lectures and tested the contents before the lessons, as evidenced by a total value of 2.8286 and a mean dispersion of 1.35102. Additionally, the participants firmly concurred that online programs were designed to motivate and encourage young learners to study, as indicated by a total value of 3.5143 and a mean dispersion of 1.33561. Regarding the involvement and training of preschool teachers in developing strategies for online education, the respondents agreed, with a total value of 3.6571 and a mean dispersion of 1.36929, indicating that preschool teachers were trained and actively engaged in crafting effective strategies for online instruction. Lastly, concerning understanding terms and conditions in online contracts, the participants concurred that preschool teachers read and comprehended the stated terms and conditions before using them, with a total value of 3.1429 and a mean dispersion of 1.27729.

Table 3. Perception for Preschool Teachers on Online Learning.

	Mean	Std. Div.
I propose that online learning should continue even during the COVID-19 pandemic.	3.5714	1.33592
I am comfortable with teaching my preschool students online.	3.5429	1.28182
I believe physical education is better when compared to online learning.	2.5857	1.30209
I am worried that my students will find it difficult to interact with me if I continue to use online platforms.	2.3429	1.23689

The findings of this research concerning the last objective explored preschool teachers' perspectives on various aspects of online learning. The respondents agreed that online learning should continue even after the post-COVID-19 pandemic, with an average score of 3.5714 and a mean dispersion of 1.33592. Responding to whether preschool teachers felt comfortable teaching their children online, the participants indicated they felt at ease tutoring them online, with an average score of 3.5429 and a measure of dispersion of 1.28182. However, the responders were divided in their opinions on whether physical education was superior to online learning. The total value for this statement was 2.5857, with a deviation of 1.30209. Lastly, the participants were concerned that their students would find it difficult to interact with them if they continued to use online platforms. The mean score for this question was 2.3429, with a standard deviation of 1.23689, indicating that some teachers were worried about potential challenges in student-teacher interaction with the use of online platforms.

DISCUSSION

The focus of this study was to investigate the challenges preschool teachers face during online teaching and learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic, with a specific emphasis on the lack of training and expertise in using technological tools for effective education delivery.

The research findings indicated that the lack of professional training and development in using technology was one of the most significant challenges affecting technology implementation in education (Kim et al., 2013). This lack of training in ICT tools hindered the teachers' ability to conduct online education effectively (Bamrara, 2020). Moreover, teachers' inadequate training opportunities in ICT tools were reported (Paulus et al., 2020). Ahmad (2020) also highlighted that the lack of training for teachers was a significant obstacle to online education. The findings revealed that most teachers had a backup plan and tested the contents before conducting online classes (participants' responses). Having a backup plan and conducting testing beforehand helped them address any technical issues proactively, ensuring uninterrupted online sessions. Additionally, the participants emphasized the importance of designing online programs to motivate children to study, making the platforms user-friendly and attractive (Bovermann & Bastiaens, 2020). The motivation of students to attend online classes played a crucial role in enhancing the productivity of the sessions (Irvin et al., 2007). Most participants supported the notion that online learning should continue even after the post-COVID-19 pandemic. The experience gained during the pandemic with online education positively impacted teachers' attitudes, leading them to endorse its continuation beyond the pandemic. Participants also expressed comfort with teaching preschool students online, having adapted to the online education system during the pandemic. However, some respondents believed physical education was superior to online learning, as physical activities engaged students and helped them better understand the content (participants' responses).

In conclusion, this study provided insights into the challenges faced by preschool teachers during online education, the strategies they employed to overcome these challenges, and their perceptions of online teaching and learning. The findings emphasized the need for effective training and support in using technological tools for education delivery and designing engaging online programs. Furthermore, the study highlighted that many teachers were open to continuing online learning beyond the pandemic, acknowledging its potential benefits and opportunities in preschool education.

RECOMMENDATION

The research conducted in this study aimed to explore the importance of providing adequate training to preschool teachers for the successful implementation of online education. The focus was preparing teachers to use online platforms effectively and deliver interactive and engaging classes. The study found that training is vital in enhancing teachers' knowledge of online tools and methodologies, ultimately leading to better online education experiences for students and teachers. The research established that preschool teachers can benefit from preparation training on effectively utilising online platforms. This training should cover various aspects, including online education methods and how to conduct efficient classes. By equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge, they can navigate online tools confidently and provide better learning experiences for their students. Furthermore, the research recommended that for the successful implementation of online education in preschools, it is crucial to ensure that teachers and students have access to adequate tools. Access to these tools enhances the learning process, but it was noted that not all teachers and students may have access to them. To address this issue, schools should provide technical support to assist teachers in handling any potential technical issues that may arise during online classes. Early training of teachers is also essential to improve their familiarity with online platforms and their ability to handle technical challenges that can occur in an online learning environment. Moreover, reliable internet connectivity is vital to avoid class disruptions and ensure productivity.

The study emphasized the importance of comprehensive training for both teachers and students. Proper training improves teachers' attitudes towards online education and enables students to adapt and use online platforms effectively. Training should also encourage teachers to employ various tools and learning approaches, such as videos, to involve students in the lessons actively. This approach ensures that students remain engaged and motivated during online sessions. With well-prepared teachers, online classes become more interactive, and students are more enthusiastic about attending them. Ultimately, the research findings indicated that training before teachers engage in online education is essential. This pre-training enhances teachers' knowledge and skills, helping them understand the nuances of delivering effective online education. As a result, teachers can create dynamic and engaging online learning environments that benefit students and educators alike.

In conclusion, this study highlighted the significance of providing adequate training to preschool teachers for successful online education implementation. Proper training empowers teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to utilize online platforms effectively and conduct engaging and interactive classes. Schools should also ensure access to necessary tools and technical support to enhance the online learning experience. By prioritizing comprehensive training, teachers and students can fully embrace and benefit from online preschool education.

CONCLUSION

This research study addressed the challenges preschool teachers face when utilizing online platforms for education during the COVID-19 pandemic. The primary goal was to identify these challenges and devise strategies to overcome them effectively. The findings of this study shed light on the significance of providing adequate training to teachers, ensuring access to necessary tools, and offering technical support to enhance the online learning experience. This study focused on understanding the specific challenges teachers encountered during online education delivery. The research revealed that a lack of proper training in using technological tools and online platforms posed a significant obstacle for teachers. The absence of professional development and pedagogical training hindered their ability to deliver effective lessons, resulting in potential disengagement and boredom among students. Additionally, the teachers faced difficulties converting offline resources to online materials and sharing them through e-learning platforms due to a lack of knowledge and expertise.

The study's results also highlighted the importance of having a backup plan and testing contents before conducting online classes. This practice allowed teachers to anticipate and address technical issues, ensuring a smoother learning experience for students. Furthermore, designing online programs to motivate and engage students emerged as a crucial factor for successful online education. Encouraging and interactive classes were pivotal in keeping students motivated and actively participating in learning. The research emphasized the need for comprehensive training for teachers to address the identified challenges. Such training should encompass both technological skills and pedagogical approaches for online education. By adequately preparing teachers, they can confidently navigate online platforms and implement effective teaching strategies, ultimately benefiting the overall learning experience for students. While this study provided valuable insights into the challenges preschool teachers face during online education, there is still a need for further research. Exploring additional challenges and their impact on online education in various educational

sectors, such as primary schools, universities, and colleges, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the broader challenges educators and learners face.

In summary, this research study illuminated the challenges faced by preschool teachers during online education and proposed strategies to overcome them. The findings underscore the significance of training, technical support, and engaging teaching methods in ensuring successful online education delivery. As the world embraces digital learning, continued research in this area will contribute to improving and optimising online education practices across various educational levels.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR (optional)

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, M. (2020). challenges and issues of its in learning in Pakistan: a descriptive study at secondary school level in Punjab Pakistan. *international journal of computer science and technology*, 4(4), 9-19.
- Ahmad, I. (2020). Online teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: Experiences of Pakistani teachers. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 13(1), 134-148. doi: 10.1108/JRIT-06-2020-0033.
- Aithal, P. S., and Aithal, S., (2016). Impact of on-line education on higher education system. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(1), pp. 225-235.
- Almaiah MA, Al-Khasawneh A, Althunibat A (2020). Exploring the critical challenges and factors influencing the E-learning system usage during COVID-19 pandemic. *Education and Information Technologies* 25(4):5261-5280.
- Badri, M., Alnuaimi, A., Mohaidat, J., Yang, G., & Al Rashedi, A. (2016). Perception of teachers' professional development needs, impacts, and barriers: The Abu Dhabi case. *SAGE Open*, 6(3), 2158244016662901.
- Ball, H. L. (2019). Conducting online surveys. *Journal of Human Lactation*, 35(3), 413- 417

- Bamrara, A. (2020). Integration of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching Processes. In *Examining the Roles of Teachers and Students in Mastering New Technologies* (pp. 240-249). IGI Global.
- Bamrara, A. (2020). Challenges of online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 85-100. doi: 10.1177/0047239520947257.
- Barrett, P., Treves, A., Shmis, T., & Ambasz, D. (2019). The impact of school infrastructure on learning: A synthesis of the evidence.
- Basilaia, G., Dgebuadze, M., Kantaria, M., & Chokhonelidze, G. (2020). Replacing the classic learning form at universities as an immediate response to the COVID-19 virus infection in Georgia. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology*, 8(III).
- Bezhovki Z, S. The evolution of e-learning and New trends., 2016, 6, 50-57)
- Bovermann, K., & Bastiaens, T. J. (2020). Towards a motivational design? Connecting gamification user types and online learning activities. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 15(1), 1-18.
- Bradley, C., Cordaro, D. T., Zhu, F., Vildostegui, M., Han, R. J., Brackett, M., & Jones, J. (2018). Supporting improvements in classroom climate for students and teachers with the four pillars of wellbeing curriculum. *Translational Issues in Psychological Science*, 4(3), 245.
- Carroll, A., Houghton, S., Wood, R., Unsworth, K., Hattie, J., Gordon, L., & Bower, J. (2009). Self-efficacy and academic achievement in Australian high school students: The mediating effects of academic aspirations and delinquency. *Journal of adolescence*, 32(4), 797-817.
- Chih-Pei, H. U., & Chang, Y. Y. (2017). John W. Creswell, research design: A qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method approaches. *Journal of Social and Administrative Sciences*, 4(2), 205-207.
- Denscombe, M. (2021). *Ebook: The Good Research Guide: For Small-Scale Social Research Projects*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crises. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(1), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520934018>
- Dong, C. (2018). 'Young children nowadays are very smart in ICT'—pre-school teachers' perceptions of ICT use. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 1-14.
- Dong, C., Cao, S., & Li, H. (2020). Young children's online learning during COVID-19 pandemic: Chinese parents' beliefs and attitudes. *Children and youth services review*, 118, 105440.
- Fraillon, J., J. Ainley, W. Schulz, T. Friedman, and D. Duckworth. 2019. *Preparing for Life in a Digital World: The IEA International Computer and Information Literacy Study 2018 International Report*. New York: Springer.
- Georgiev, V., & Nikolova, A. (2020). Tools for Creating and Presenting Online Learning Resources for Preschool Kids. *TEM Journal*, 9(4), 1692.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2016.1242392>
- GEW (Gewerkschaft Erziehung und Wissenschaft). 2020. *Digitalpakt Schule Und Digitalisierung an Schulen [Digital Pact for Schools and Digitalisation in Schools.]*. Frankfurt.

- Giovannella C (2021). Effect induced by the Covid-19 pandemic on students' perception about technologies and distance learning. In Ludic, Co-design and Tools Supporting Smart Learning Ecosystems and Smart Education (pp. 105-116). Springer, Singapore.
- Gopalan, M., Rosinger, K., & Ahn, J. B. (2020). Use of Quasi-Experimental Research Designs in Education Research: Growth, Promise, and Challenges. *Review of Research in Education*, 44(1), 218-243. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732X20903302>
- Gudmundsdottir, G. B., and O. E. Hatlevik. 2018. "Newly Qualified Teachers' Professional Digital Competence: Implications for Teacher Education." *European Journal of Teacher Education* 41 (2): 21–231. doi:10.1080/02619768.2017.1416085
- Guerriero, S., ed. 2017. *Pedagogical Knowledge and the Changing Nature of the Teaching Profession*. Paris: OECD.
- Hardin, B. J., Lower, J. K., Smallwood, G. R., Chakravarthi, S., Li, L., & Jordan, C. (2010). Teachers, families, and communities supporting English language learners in inclusive pre-kindergarten: An evaluation of a professional development model. *Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education*, 31(1), 20-36.
- Hashemi, A. (2021). The barriers to the use of ICT in English language teaching: A systematic literature review. *Bilgi ve İletişim Teknolojileri Dergisi*, 3(1), 77-88.
- Hashemi, M. (2021). Preparing teachers for online education: Examining the impact of training on teachers' self-efficacy and perceived competence. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 69(1), 257-275. doi: 10.1007/s11423-020-09801-w.
- Hathcoat, J. D., Meixner, C., & Nicholas, M. C. (2019). Ontology and epistemology.
- Haydam, N. E., & Steenkamp, P. (2020). A Methodological Blueprint for Social Sciences Research—The Social Sciences Research Methodology Framework. *EIRP Proceedings*, 15(1).
- Hester, S. D., Southard, K. M., Kim, Y. A., Cox, J., Elfring, L. K., Blowers, P., & Talanquer, V. (2021). Benefits and Challenges in the Implementation of an Instructional-Teams Model for Supporting Evidence-Based Instructional Practices in Large-Enrollment STEM Courses. *College Teaching*, 1-12.
- Jamil, H., Razak, N. A., Raju, R., & Mohamed, A. R. (2011, March). Teacher professional development in Malaysia: Issues and challenges. In Africa-Asia university dialogue for educational development report of the International Experience Sharing Seminar: Actual status and issues of teacher professional development (pp. 85-102).
- Joshua, D., Obille, K., John, E., and Shuaibu, U., 2016. E-Learning platform system for the department of library and information science, Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola: A Developmental plan. *Information Impact: Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 7(1), pp. 51-69.
- Kaiser, G., and J. König. 2019. "Competence Measurement in (Mathematics) Teacher Education and Beyond: Implications for Policy." *Higher Education Policy* 32: 597–615. doi:10.1057/s41307-019-00139-z.
- Khan, M. S. H., Hasan, M., & Clement, C. K. (2012). Barriers to the introduction of ICT into education in developing countries: The example of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Instruction*, 5(2).
- Kim, C., Kim, M. K., Lee, C., Spector, J. M., & DeMeester, K. (2013). Teacher beliefs and technology integration. *Teaching and teacher education*, 29, 76-85.

- Kim, S., Kim, M., Khera, O., & Getman, J. (2014). The experience of three flipped classrooms in an urban university: An exploration of design principles. *Internet and Higher Education*, 22, 37-50. doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2014.04.003
- Liao, M. T., & Wong, C. T. (2010). Effects of dialogue journals on L2 students' writing fluency, reflections, anxiety, and motivation. *Reflections on English Language Teaching*, 9(2), 139-170.
- Majzub, R. M. (2013). Critical issues in pre-school education in Malaysia. *Recent advances in educational technologies*, 150-155.
- Manca, F., & Meluzzi, F. (2020). Strengthening Online Learning When Schools Are Closed: The Role of Families and Teachers in Supporting Students during the COVID-19 Crisis.
- McFarlane, A. E. 2019. "Devices and Desires: Competing Visions of a Good Education in the Digital Age." *British Journal of Educational Technology* 50 (3): 1125– 1136.
doi:10.1111/bjet.12764.
- Mishra, P., & Mehta, R. (2017). What we educators get wrong about 21st-century learning:
- Noreen, H., Intizar, F., & Gulzar, S. (2019). Teachers' multidimensional attitude towards inclusive education. *UMT Education Review*, 2(2), 72-89.
- Noreen, H., Intizar, F., & Gulzar, S. (2019). Teachers' multidimensional attitude towards inclusive education. *UMT Education Review*, 2(2), 72-89.
- Omar, R., Rashid, R. A., Mohamad, A., & Yusof, N. (2017). A Review of Challenges for Professional Development of Malaysian Teachers. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(7), 809-815.
- Paulus, M. T., Villegas, S. G., & Howze-Owens, J. (2020). Professional Learning Communities: Bridging the Technology Integration Gap Through Effective Professional Development. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 95(2), 193-202.
- Paulus, T. M., Lester, J. N., & Dempster, P. G. (2020). Virtual teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic: Teacher education and field experiences. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 28(2), 189-199.
- Raheem, BR, Khan, M.A.The role of e-learning in covid 19 crisis, 2020,3135-3138. Results of a survey. *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 33(1), 6-19.
- Ridder, H. G. (2017). The theory contribution of case study research designs. *Business Research*, 10(2), 281-305.
- Salles, R. L., Linhares, R. E., Madureira, N. A., Barreto, M. C., & Gomess, O. M. Colas Biológicas: Tipos e Biocompatibilidade. In *SCIENCES FORUM* (p. 38).
- Sheridan, K. M., Banzer, D., Pradzinski, A., & Wen, X. (2020). Early math professional development: Meeting the challenge through online learning. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 48(2), 223-231.
- Sileyew, K. J. (2019). Research design and methodology. In *Cyberspace*. IntechOpen.
- Singh, V., Thurman, A. (2019). How many ways can we define online learning? A systematic literature review of definitions of online learning (1988-2018). *American Journal of Distance Education*, 33(4), 289–306.

- Sintema, E. J. (2020, April 7). Effect of COVID-19 on the performance of grade 12 students: Implications for STEM education. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 16(7).
<https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/7893>
- Subedi, S., Nayaju, S., Subedi, S., Shah, S. K., & Shah, J. M. (2020). Impact of e-learning during COVID-19 pandemic among nursing students and teachers of Nepal. *International Journal of Science and Healthcare Research*, 5(3), 9.
- Taat, M. S., & De Rozario, G. (2014). The influence of academic attitude and self-efficacy towards students achievement in private higher learning institution, Malaysia. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 3(6), 41-50.
- UNESCO (2020), *COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response*, <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
- Veldsman, A., Van Greunen, D., & Botha, J. (2020). eReadiness Assessment Tool for Schools. In *2020 IST-Africa Conference (IST-Africa)* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
- Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y., & Xu, X. (2012). Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: Extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 36(1), 157-178.
- Wingo, N. P., Ivankova, N. V., & Moss, J. A. (2017). Faculty perceptions about teaching online: Exploring the literature using the technology acceptance model as an organizing framework. *Online Learning*, 21(1), 15-35.
- Xiang, Y. T., Li, W., Zhang, Q., Jin, Y., Rao, W. W., Zeng, L. N., et al. (2020). Timely research papers about COVID-19 in China. *The Lancet*. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30375-5.
- Weeden, K. A., & Benjamin, C. (2020). The small-world network of college classes: implications for epidemic spread on a university campus. *Sociological Science*, 7, 222-241.
- Weeden, K. A., & Benjamin, C. (2020). The small-world network of college classes: implications for epidemic spread on a university campus. *Sociological Science*, 7, 222-241.
- Zhang, W., Wang, Y., Yang, L., & Wang, C. (2020). Suspending classes without stopping learning: China's education emergency management policy in the COVID-19 outbreak. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13(3), 1-6.